

Synthesis and structural {IR, ^1H NMR, FAB-MS, XRD and magnetic} studies of some lanthanide complexes with salicylidene-2-aminopyridine

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Abstract : Lanthanide complexes of the type $[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Ln}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (1-3) and $[(\text{Cl})\text{Ln}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ (4-6) [where Ln = Gd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Y^{III}, L = Schiff base ligand; salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (sapH)] were synthesized and characterized by various physico-chemical techniques. The complexes were found to be coloured solid and were highly soluble only in DMF and DMSO. These complexes have been characterized by elemental (Ln, C, H, N and Cl) analysis and spectral (IR, ^1H NMR and FAB-MS) data, and magnetic studies; whereas the structural composition of the complex have been determined by FAB-MS spectral studies and X-ray diffraction studies of the complex $[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Y}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (3) was found to be 252.054 Å.

Keywords : Lanthanum(III) chloride, Schiff base complex, FAB-MS, IR, UV-Visible, ^1H NMR, XRD studies.

Introduction

The coordination chemistry of Schiff bases derived from heterocyclic systems constitute a remarkably versatile class of compounds with diverse analytical, technological and biological applications¹⁻⁴. Metal complexes of heterocyclic Schiff bases of lanthanides have received comparatively less attention so far⁵. Lanthanide complexes show biological activities⁶⁻⁸, pharmacological applications^{9,10} and antibacterial¹¹ properties. Metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and various amines have been widely investigated^{12,13}. A limited attention has been given, to the complexes of neodymium(III) and lanthanum(III) metals only, containing salicylidene-2-aminopyridine ligand recently in our laboratories¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Keeping above facts in view, we report herein the synthesis and characterization of lanthanide complexes containing salicylidene-2-aminopyridine.

Results and discussion

Infrared spectra :

The ligand used in the present investigation possess two potential donor sites : (i) the phenolic oxygen and (ii) the azomethine nitrogen. The infrared spectrum of the ligand sapH exhibited characteristic^{18,19} bands in the region 3343

cm^{-1} stretching frequency, due to the presence of (phenolic) -OH group of the ligand. These bands have been disappeared in the spectra of the complexes suggesting the bonding through 'O' atom of the phenolic -OH after deprotonation. The ligand also showed a strong band 1621 cm^{-1} , assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ vibrations after coordination is shifted to higher frequency region 1667-1625 cm^{-1} . This negative shift shows the participation of the azomethine nitrogen²⁰ in the coordination with lanthanide metal. The $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ band observed in the range 1296-1278 cm^{-1} which indicate that the bonding takes place through phenolic oxygen after deprotonation of -OH group. The spectral data (Table 4) of all the complexes, showed bands observed in the region 3350-3691 cm^{-1} , which can be ascribed to ν_{OH} stretching frequencies in the spectra of the complexes. After drying the complexes at around 120 °C it showed shift in this band to \sim 3379-3428 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of coordinated water. The infrared frequencies, for $\nu_{\text{Ln}-\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Ln}-\text{Cl}}$, have been observed in the range 485-366 and 322-311 cm^{-1} respectively.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectral bands of samarium(III) complex; $[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Sm}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (2) observed at 24874-20962 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the transitions $^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow ^4\text{I}_{11/2}$ and

${}^6H_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^4K_{11/2}$ energy levels respectively. Comparing the above transitions for these complex to that of the corresponding aquo ions, the electronic spectral data are found to be shifted towards lower energy region. The electronic spectral parameters of the above complex have been calculated by literature procedure^{21,23}. On the basis of the above observation it is being concluded that the coordination number of the present complex is eight. Various parameters have been calculated for the above complex and are given below : nephelauxetic ratio ($\beta = 0.94907$), bonding parameter ($b^{1/2} = 0.0881$), Sinha's covalence parameter ($\delta = 0.9387$) and angular covalence ($\eta = 0.0047$).

Magnetic studies :

The paramagnetic behavior of the lanthanide(III) ions are consistent with the presence of unpaired '4f' electrons. All these solid complexes of yttrium(III) chloride $[(Cl)_2Y(L)(H_2O)_4]$ (**3**) and $[(Cl)Y(L)_2(H_2O)_3]$ (**6**) are diamagnetic at room temperature, whereas gadolinium(III) and samarium(III) chloride complexes of Schiff base exhibit paramagnetism and observed magnetic moment value in the range 7.72 and 1.60 B.M respectively.

1H NMR spectra :

1H NMR spectrum of the Schiff base ligand, sapH a sharp signals observed at δ 8.47 ppm, correspond to the azomethine proton which on complexation undergoes some shielding due to change and gave signal at δ 9.45 ppm in the corresponding complex. A strong signal appeared in the region δ 12.40 ppm, may be attributed to the phenolic proton (OH) of the ligand, whereas 1H NMR spectra of the corresponding metal complex are devoid of signals due to -OH proton indicating bonding to metal through phenolic oxygen after deprotonation²⁴.

The NMR spectrum of ligand (Table 1) exhibited signals due to -OH aromatic protons in the region δ 7.33–6.40 ppm, which are shielded compared to the free ligands probably due to high order of distortion of the aromatic rings as a result of the complex formation with metal²⁴.

FAB-mass spectrum of (salicylidene-2-aminopyridine)-yttrium(III) chloride :

The FAB-MS spectrum and the fragmentation^{25,26} pattern of the ligand (sapH) have been reported earlier. The molecular ion peaks in the mass spectrum of yttrium(III) complex, (salicylidene-2-aminopyridine)-

Table 1. 1H NMR chemical shifts (δ , ppm) for the Schiff base, ligand and their yttrium(III) complex (**3**) in DMSO- d_6 with their assignments

Schiff base/ complex	δ OH (s)	δ H _a (s)	δ H _b (3H, t, H _b)	δ H (m) (8H, m, H ₁ -H ₈)
Ligand (sapH)	12.40	8.47	2.32	7.33–6.79
$[(Cl)_2Y(sap)-$ $(H_2O)_4]$ (3)	-	9.45	2.50	7.87–6.40

yttrium(III) chloride, $[(Cl)_2Y(L)(H_2O)_4]$ (**3**) are shown in Fig. 1 and fragmentation pattern in Scheme 1. The molecular ion peak for $[(Cl)_2Y(L)(H_2O)_4]^+$ observed at m/z 429. The other important peaks observed at m/z 393, 375, 357, 287, 209, 104, 90. The most prominent molecular ion peak observed at m/z 90 correspond to $[Y^+]$.

X-Ray powder diffraction studies :

X-Ray diffraction (PXRD) were carried out on Rigaku D/max-2200 PC diffractometer instrument operating with Cu-K α_1 radiation ($\delta = 1.540556 \text{ \AA}$). The powder XRD patterns were recorded in the 2θ range between 20–80° which have shown in Fig. 2. The average crystallite size was calculated from the diffraction line width based on the Scherrer relation. Spectrum clearly showed that the materials prepared are crystalline in nature. Non uniform broadening of lines is attributed to anisotropic crystallites. The line broadening is used here to calculate the crystallite size using Debye Scherres formula in Table 2.

Experimental

Synthesis of Schiff bases :

The ligand²⁷ was prepared by addition of equimolar amounts of salicylaldehyde (5.73 g; 46.92 mmol) and 2-aminopyridine (4.416 g; 46.92 mmol) in methanol (30 cm³); with stirring for (~ 1 h) followed by refluxing for ~ 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled at room temperature to afford orange crystals, separated compound was

Fig. 1. FAB mass spectrum of (salicylidene-2-aminopyridine)yttrium(III) chloride, $[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Y}(\text{sap})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (3).

Scheme 1. Fragmentation pattern of (salicylidene-2-aminopyridine)yttrium(III) chloride, $[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Y}(\text{sap})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (3).

recrystallized in ethanol (*sapH*), yield 75%, m.p. 65 °C.

Synthesis of complexes :

The methanolic solution of hydrated metal chloride, $\text{GdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.5 g; 1.35 mmol) was added to the methanolic solution of Schiff base *sapH* (0.285 g; 1.35 mmol) in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio(s), followed by the addition of saturated ethanolic solution of KOH (0.076 g; 1.35 mmol) during which time a cream precipitate was ob-

tained. Further, it was refluxed for ~ 10 h. The excess of solvent was removed by distillation, followed by addition of pet-ether (~ 10 cm^3). The precipitate was filtered off, and dried *in vacuo*. The crude product was washed with ethanol for several times to remove unreacted metal chloride. It was washed with diethyl ether. The compound were obtained, when the lanthanum chloride (Gd, Sm and Y) were reacted in 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratio

Fig. 2. The powdered X-ray diffraction spectrum of complex $[(Cl)_2Y(sap)(H_2O)_4]$ (3).

Table 2. Calculated XRD parameters of yttrium(III) complex (3)

Parameters	$[(Cl)_2Y(L)(H_2O)_4]$ (3)
Crystallite size	252.054 Å
Empirical formula	$[(Cl)_2YC_{12}H_{17}O_5N_2]$
Formula weight	429
Powder used	1.6 Kw
Wave length	1.540 Å

under similar condition and these complexes were collected in Table 3.

The new complexes $[(Cl)_2Ln(L)(H_2O)_4]$ and $[(Cl)Ln(L)_2(H_2O)_3]$ have been synthesized by the reaction of $LnCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ with corresponding Schiff bases in methanol. The complexes thus formed are represented by the following chemical equations :

when above reaction was carried out in 1 : 3 : 3 molar ratio, desired product could not be obtained. Only 1 : 2 : 2 products could be isolated and further identified by elemental analysis : [where $Ln = Gd^{III}$, Sm^{III} and Y^{III} ; $L =$ Schiff base (salicylidene-2-aminopyridine) (*sapH*)].

All these complexes are soluble only in DMF and DMSO but insoluble in other common organic solvents. The complexes are air stable at room temperature and decomposed at around 295–145 °C. The structures and properties of the Schiff base ligand and their metal complexes were confirmed by IR and elemental analysis. Further, the structural composition of the ligand and complexes were confirmed by FAB-MS spectra.

Physical measurements :

The metal chlorides ($LnCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$) were obtained from Loba and used as such. The solvents were purified using standard procedure²⁸. The metals after destroying the organic matter by successive treatment of fuming nitric acid/aqua regia were precipitated as carbonate and determined as Ln_2O_3 . Chloride was determined by Volhard's method²⁹. FAB-MS spectra were recorded on a Jeol SX

Table 3. Synthetic, physical and analytical data of lanthanide metal complexes

Sl. no.	Molecular formula of complexes; (% Yield)	Physical state and colour	M.p./D.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					$\mu_{\text{effective}}$ (B.M.)
				Metal	Chlorine	Carbon	Hydrogen	Nitrogen	
	$[\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}]$ 69%	Orange yellow	65	-	-	72.60 (72.70)	5.06 (5.07)	14.10 (14.13)	-
1.	$[(\text{Cl})_2\text{GdC}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5]$ (1) 61	Greenish yellow Powdered solid	145	35.26 (35.36)	6.88 (7.88)	32.41 (32.43)	3.73 (3.83)	6.29 (6.31)	7.72
2.	$[(\text{Cl})_2\text{SmC}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5]$ (2) 54	Yellowish green Powdered solid	295	30.51 (30.61)	14.19 (14.29)	29.28 (29.39)	3.36 (3.47)	5.61 (5.71)	1.60
3.	$[(\text{Cl})_2\text{YC}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5]$ (3) 54	Yellowish brown Powdered solid	295	20.65 (20.75)	16.22 (16.32)	33.47 (33.57)	3.86 (3.96)	6.43 (6.53)	Diamagnetic
4.	$[(\text{Cl})\text{GdC}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5]$ (4) 38	Yellow Powdered solid	240	24.35 (24.45)	5.41 (5.45)	44.76 (44.86)	3.64 (3.74)	8.62 (8.72)	7.65
5.	$[(\text{Cl})\text{SmC}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5]$ (5) 38	Dirty white Powdered solid	275	23.51 (23.62)	5.41 (5.51)	45.25 (45.35)	3.68 (3.78)	8.72 (8.82)	1.62
6.	$[(\text{Cl})\text{YC}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5]$ (6) 57	Light yellow Powdered solid	280	15.41 (15.51)	6.01 (6.09)	50.10 (50.17)	4.16 (4.18)	9.56 (9.76)	Diamagnetic

Table 4. The infrared frequencies (cm^{-1}) of the lanthanide(III) complexes with salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (*sapH*) Schiff base

Sl. no.	Complex	$\nu_{\text{Ln-Cl}}$	$\nu_{\text{Ln-N}}$	ν_{OH}	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$
1.	$[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Gd}(\text{sap})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (1)	311	475	3420	1628	1278
2.	$[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Sm}(\text{sap})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (2)	322	485	3410	1635	1285
3.	$[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Y}(\text{sap})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (3)	-	-	3691	1663	1285
4.	$[(\text{Cl})\text{Gd}(\text{sap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ (4)	326	416	3412	1628	1296
5.	$[(\text{Cl})\text{Sm}(\text{sap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ (5)	320	444	3350	1625	1280
6.	$[(\text{Cl})\text{Y}(\text{sap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ (6)	-	-	3650	1667	1290

102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 KV, 10 MA) as the FAB gas. The NMR spectrum was recorded on a Jeol-AL-300 FT-NMR spectrometer in DMSO- d_6 using TMS as the internal standard. The infrared spectra were obtained in KBr discs on a Jasco FT/IR-5300 spectrophotometer. Magnetic moments at room temperature have been measured as reported earlier^{30,31}.

Conclusion :

Eight coordinated lanthanide Schiff base complexes of the type $[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Ln}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ and $[(\text{Cl})\text{Ln}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ were prepared respectively. The ligand *sapH* was found to coordinate with lanthanides, in a bidentate manner; bonding takes place through phenolate oxygen and azomethine nitrogen. A eight coordinate geometry for $[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Y}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (3) have been tentatively proposed. FAB-MS studies of $[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Y}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (3) complex produced $m/z = 429$. The conclusion regarding the structure

of these complexes in solid state would be possible only after single X-ray crystallographic studies, which have not been successful so far. However, formula of the complex 3 has been suggested by spectral (IR, electronic, NMR and FAB-mass) studies.

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